

GEOGRAPHICAL POSITION AND POLEOGEOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF LOWER ZARAFSHAN VALLEY

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N.U. Kholmatov*

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the paleogeographic features of the Lower Zarafshan Valley during the Neolithic period, based on a review of archaeological literature.

Introduction.

The hydrology of the lower reaches of the Zarafshan River includes tributaries such as the Mohandarya, Khojayli, Echkiliksay, and Ayaqagitma. Since there are no mountains preventing water from filling the depressions of the Kyzylkum, conditions allowed the formation of water basins across this latitude, thereby enhancing the activity of the aforementioned watercourses. However, the presence of the Sultan Uvays Mountain in the Akchadarya basin, extending 25 km to the east, created a dual paleogeographic scenario. Due to its orientation, the area between Shurakhan and the Aral Sea was divided into right and left sectors through the influence of the Amu Darya.

According to geographical literature, the paleogeography of the Lower Zarafshan Valley was shaped by geological processes during the Neogene stage of the Quaternary period. This resulted in a diverse range of natural-geographical zones such as Bukhara-Qorako'l, Gazli, and Sanduqli¹[1, p.229].

Since the 1950s, the Khorezm Expedition under the leadership of S.P. Tolstov, and later under Y.G. Ghulomov, carried out comprehensive archaeological investigations in the lower Zarafshan basin. However, publications from these studies provide limited historical data on Paleolithic settlements.

By the mid-1970s, members of the Khorezm archaeological-ethnographic expedition began uncovering open-type Paleolithic sites such as Burli-3 at the foothills of Sultan Uvays on the left bank of the Amu Darya. Cultural layers from the Late Stone Age revealed material remains of hunting-gathering communities, indicating active ethnic interactions. During the

¹ Baratov, P. *Natural Geography of Uzbekistan*. Tashkent, 1996 – pp. 170–180.

Würm glaciation of the Pleistocene, demographic growth in the Burli-3 settlement likely drove the expansion into the right-bank areas, suggesting that the geographic environment, climate, and natural resources were conducive to daily subsistence activities².

Works by S.P. Tolstov and A.V. Vinogradov describe that during the 6th–5th millennia BCE, the southern Akchadarya region witnessed rising Amu Darya water levels, resulting in overflow into the Kyzylkum desert. The formation of interconnected or isolated water basins among the dunes allowed for human settlement. Artifacts from the Jonbos-4 site (26x17 m), an artificially constructed settlement using wood, reeds, mud, and other materials, are considered key sources in the study of paleohydrology, paleogeography, paleoethnography, and ethno-demography³.

In his research on the Neolithic history of the Khorezm oasis, A.V. Vinogradov documented the spread of kin-based communities from the Jonbos-4 site into the Tuyamo'yin region, describing surface and semi-subterranean dwellings with circular or rectangular floor plans (e.g., Jonbos group: Jonbos-31,5,11,12,14,18; Qavat group: Qavat-7, Bayram-Qoziqon-6; Ma'mur group: Ma'mur-1,3,4,3B,4; Kunek-1,3; Dingilja-6; Qo'rg'oshin group; and Tadjikazgan group: Tadjikazgan-2,3,6,6a,10,13,14)⁴.

His monograph also includes evidence of Paleolithic, Mesolithic, and Neolithic settlements in the interfluvium of the Amu Darya and Syr Darya. However, there is a notable absence of Stone Age and Mesolithic sites in the Lower Zarafshan Valley. Conversely, the early Neolithic site Uchashi-131 on the banks of the Daryosoy tributary and Darbozaqir I, II (dated to the 4th–3rd millennia BCE) provide insights into the earliest settlement in the region⁵.

In his monograph, N.U. Kholmatov discusses the paleogeography and paleo-climate of the Lower Zarafshan basin and addresses Mesolithic and Neolithic archaeological sites such as Chorbakti-II, 23, 27, 41, and others along the Daryosoy system (e.g., Uchashi-31, Darbozaqir-1,2, Chorbakti-13,14,15A,15B,16,18,20,21). M.A. Itina's work highlights the geographical positioning and ethnic processes surrounding the Tuyamo'yin area on the left bank of the Amu Darya, documenting sites like Qo'shbuloq, Karri-Qizil, and Sultan Sanjar that emerged due to flooding⁶.

² Baratov, P., Mamatqulov, M., Rafiqov, A. *Natural Geography of Central Asia*. Tashkent: O'qituvchi Publishing House, 2002 – pp. 229–335. Vinogradova, E.A. “First Paleolithic Finds in the Sultan Uvays Area” // *The Aral Sea Region in Antiquity and the Middle Ages* – Moscow: Institute of Oriental Studies, Russian Academy of Sciences, Nauka, 1998 – pp. 74–77. Matyakubov, Kh.Kh. *The Bronze and Early Iron Ages in the Khorezm Oasis: Problems of Culture, Socio-Economic, and Political Relations*. Tashkent: Publishing House of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, 2017 – p. 14. *History of Khorezm Civilization*. Nukus: Karakalpakstan Publishing, 2017 – p. 42.

³ Tolstov, S.P. *Ancient Khorezm*. Moscow: Nauka, Moscow State University, 1948 – pp. 59–65. Kholmatov, N.U., Kholmatova, Z.N. “On the Neolithic Period in the Akchadarya Basin” // *History of Khorezm*. Tashkent-Urgench: Navruz, 2019 – pp. 180–181. *History of Uzbekistan*. Tashkent, 2023 – pp. 40–41.

⁴ Vinogradov, A.V. *Neolithic Sites of Khorezm*. Moscow: Nauka, 1968 – pp. 25–125.

⁵ Vinogradov, A.V. *Ancient Hunters and Fishermen of the Central Asian Interfluvium*. Moscow: Nauka, 1981. Issue XIII – pp. 46–116.

⁶ Itina, M.A. “Sites from the Neolithic and Bronze Ages” // *Antiquities of Southern Khorezm // Proceedings of the Khorezm Archaeological-Ethnographic Expedition*. Moscow, 1991. Issue XVI – pp. 66–72. Sobirov, Q. *Defense Structures of Khorezm's Villages and Cities*. Tashkent: Fan Publishing House, 2009 – p. 83. Martinez Ferreras, V., Abdullaev, O.I. *Ethnic Processes during the Primitive Communal System in Central Asia*. 2021 – pp. 423–424.

Thus, archaeological sources confirm that kin-based Neolithic communities inhabited the Lower Amu Darya and Lower Zarafshan valleys, adapting to environmental changes, natural resources, and river flooding by constructing surface dwellings and semi-subterranean shelters. Floods from the Amu Darya spilled into Kyzylkum's depressions, with Akchadarya's rising waters depositing silt and forming fertile plains.

Chemical Composition of Silt

Component	Zarafshan	Amu Darya	Syr Darya
Silicon Dioxide	52.40%	50.0%	45.32%
Sesquioxides	18.80%	17.60%	17.50%
Iron Oxide	5.07%	2.47%	2.43%
Aluminum	13.53%	15.0%	14.90%
Phosphorus Oxide	0.18%	0.13%	0.08%
Lime (CaO)	10.81%	12.0%	14.70%
Magnesium	3.44%	1.81%	1.94%
Sodium	1.76%	1.64%	2.34%
Potassium Oxide	2.47%	1.21%	1.5%

This data confirms that the Zarafshan River carries a high concentration of minerals, contributing significantly to the fertility of its floodplain⁷.

Despite the broad geographical scope of Neolithic settlements in the Bukhara-Qorako'l region, scholars have not sufficiently addressed the origin of these communities or whether sites like Darbozaqir were established by indigenous groups or migrants.

According to N.U. Kholmatov, the Uchashi-131 site on the banks of the Daryosoy is dated to the end of the 7th to the middle of the 5th millennium BCE and marks the onset of early ethnic processes⁸. However, questions remain regarding whether these communities were native or migrants drawn to the region due to stable water sources. The article hypothesizes that these groups may have descended from Upper Zarafshan hunters who settled along the Daryosoy tributary, adapting to new environmental conditions and expanding into areas like Tuzkon due to Mohandarya flooding⁹.

Archaeological findings from the Lavlakan Neolithic complex within the Kyzylkum interior and the Sakan culture of the Middle Zarafshan (e.g., Sag'an-1,2, Jangal-1, Tepaqo'l-3,4,5, Zamichatosh, Ohalik, Ochilgor) reveal that communities living in these areas adapted to anthropogenic landscape changes and engaged in ongoing ethnic interactions. These transformations became more pronounced during the second half of the 2nd millennium BCE across Uzbekistan's historical and geographical regions, leading to the formation of distinct economic-cultural types.

Conclusion. Two major settlement models emerged:

⁷ G'ulomov, Ya.G'. *The History of Irrigation in Khorezm*. Tashkent: Fan Publishing House, 1959 – pp. 24–25.

⁸ Kholmatov, N.U. *Material Culture of Neolithic Communities in Uzbekistan*. Tashkent: Fan Publishing House, 2008 – p. 18

⁹ *History of Uzbekistan*. Tashkent: 2023. Vol. II – pp. 40–46.

1. **Ferghana and Surkhandarya Regions** – Characterized by sedentary populations practicing irrigated agriculture and earthen architecture. Notable micro-oases such as Chust (4 ha) and Sopollitepa (4 ha) were established.

Ustyurt, Lower Amu Darya, Lower Zarafshan, and Tashkent Valleys – Populated by kin-based communities inhabiting mountainous caves and plains near springs. These communities shaped the physical landscape through their interaction with the environment, and their influence persisted into historical societal development.

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